

Psychosocial Determinants of School Violent Behavior and the Efficacy of Covert Sensitization in Combination with Systematic approach Therapy among Male Students in Lagos Metropolis: Implications for Student Counselors

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Abstract : The study investigated psychosocial determinants 'attitudes and self-esteem' of school violent behaviors and the efficacy of covert sensitization therapy in combination with systematic approach therapy among male students in Lagos metropolis. Ex-post facto experimental research design was adopted for the study. The samples consisted of 39 school violent behavior students identified through the School Disciplinary Record Books and another 39 non-school violent behavior students identified through randomization. The two groups were from four randomly selected Public Senior Secondary Schools. School Violent Behavior Attitudes Scale (SVBAS) and School Violent Behavior Self-Esteem Scale (SVBSES) were used to collect data for the study. Face and Content validity with the Reliability coefficient of 0.772 for SVBAS and 0.813 for SVBSES were obtained. The results showed that the attitude of school violent behavior students do not significantly differ from that of school non-violent behavior students; the self-esteem of school violent behavior students differs significantly from that of school non-violent behavior students and that Covert Sensitization therapy in combination with Systematic Approach therapy were effective in modifying the self-esteem and attitude of school violent behavior students as surf iced in the pre-test and post-test analysis of school violent behavior students' responses. The School counselors can modify male school violent behaviors that are traced to attitude and self-esteem with Covert Sensitization therapy in combination with Systematic Approach therapy in metropolitan areas.

Keywords : psychosocial determinants, violent behavior, covert sensitization therapy, systematic approach therapy

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